

Philosophical and Moral Aspects of Amir Temur's Foreign Policy

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Abstract: This article tries to reveal the philosophical aspects of Amir Temur's foreign policy and diplomacy. Amir Temur, known to the world, was a powerful politician and diplomat. He was considered the most famous ruler of the Middle Ages who united Eastern and Western countries in trade, economy and other fields. The article deeply analyzes the methods, ideas, initiative and other aspects of Amir Temur's diplomacy.

Keywords: Diplomacy, foreign policy, defense, Golden Horde, Great Silk Road, international relations.

Introduction

From his early political career until his death, Amir Temur gained nine-tenths of his power due to his diplomatic potential. Amir Temur's successors, such as Mironshah Mirzo, Ulughbek Mirzo, Shahrukh Mirzo, Husayn Boygaro, great statesmen, followed Amir Temur's diplomatic heritage and followed his path in internal and external relations. In accordance with our Turkish statehood, our ancestors followed the rules of international relations and diplomacy from time immemorial and accepted them as sacred concepts. In particular, the era of Amir Temur is the most flourishing period in the history of national international relations and diplomacy. During this period, the never-ending theoretical foundations of international and diplomatic science were reworked, combining new standards with practice, and this unique historical heritage of ours served the well-being of humanity on earth. Peace, mutual respect, compassion for one's opponent and creating a great opportunity for him, valuing the ambassador even in any difficult situation, strict adherence to the rules of diplomacy, inviolability of human life, humanism are the main features of Amir Temur's diplomacy. Despite the fact that the founder Amir Temur and the diplomatic relations of the Timurid era are being studied by researchers, we believe that these works were written as a prelude to the diplomatic activity of Amir Temur.² Because it is difficult to reveal all aspects of this heritage of Amir Temur even in several volumes of fundamental studies.

Asking the question of how the ideas and characteristics of diplomacy of Amir Temur and the Timurid period differ from the ideas and characteristics of diplomacy conducted by other countries at that time will help us to understand the issue more fully.

Literature analysis and methodology

Fathi al-Guwayli, an Egyptian researcher, rightly stated that "diplomatic methods used by Amir Temur in his relations with the leaders of other countries and some of their subtleties are worth studying in depth from a theoretical and practical point of view."³

What is the reason for Amir Temur's diplomatic potential to increase to the level of art? Fathi Al-Guwayli said, "Amir Temur is characterized by deep intelligence and intelligence, and these qualities are the most important aspect and foundation of a diplomat. Amir Temur sent his ambassadors to one

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² Karimov F., Khabibullaev A. Diplomatic relations between Amir Temur and the state of the Timurids. // Society and management, 1998, No. 1. Pages 34-35

³ Fathi Al-Guwayli. Diplomacy of Amir Temur..., 108 pages.

or another country, received the ambassadors of other countries, established diplomatic correspondence with the king and emirs, and further enriched the form and content of this field.”⁴

Amir Temur achieved the main part of his success on the world level through his diplomatic activities. The ideas of Amir Temur's diplomacy were common to his state ideology, humanitarianism was the main idea, and he always strictly followed the criteria of international diplomacy. "There is no death for an ambassador" was the great motto of Amir Temur, and he followed this rule even in the most difficult situations.

Amir Temur's diplomacy was based on bravery, courage, initiative and overall good qualities. Sakhbikiron showed great respect to his defeated opponent in any situation. The main idea in his diplomacy was to build a single space and strengthen integration, which is rising today. On a deeper level, his diplomacy is the best diplomacy of his time, he creatively developed this field, enriched it to an incomparable level, and built a bridge between cultures through it.

Today, Sakhbikiron is interpreted as the first theorist and exponent of integration. Today's "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan" also shows that the administration relies on Amir Temur's policy. In our opinion, his determination, perseverance, striving for the goal and making the most of the opportunity, quickness, are factors of his diplomatic success. Resolving conflicts through negotiations was the main idea of Amir Temur's diplomacy, and his strategic genius served to strengthen his diplomacy. Another reason for his success in this field is that Sahibkiran established diplomatic relations based on advice and council.

Discussion

Amir Temur's diplomatic tactics and ideas combined historical diplomacy, diplomatic thinking of his time, new theoretical and practical rules.

He took the path of diplomacy and allowed his opponent to come to the right conclusion. He was a forgiving diplomat who followed the path of generosity, patience, forgiveness, and tolerance for indulgence. In any situation, the main idea of his diplomacy was to achieve the goal without loss or damage. Another of his achievements is that, depending on the situation, he used such methods of diplomacy as exhortation, warning, intimidation and publicity. He skillfully exploited the weaknesses of his opponents and achieved victories through the right diplomatic measures. Another distinguishing feature of his diplomacy is that he paid special attention to the issue of choosing ambassadors and understood them as symbols of the nation and country. Accordingly, the diplomatic corps in the palace of Amir Temur was perfectly organized, acted regularly, and diplomatic relations in the state of Amir Temur were conducted personally on behalf of Amir Temur. It is worth noting that international meetings and official ceremonies were held on the basis of clear and artistically designed rules. The enrichment of these rules with high architectural and artistic solutions, the achievements of ethics, aesthetics has also acquired significance in statehood.

Also, at diplomatic official ceremonies, table setting and eating rules were strictly observed, and this direction was also elevated to the rank of art.

During this period, women also played a big role in improving diplomatic relations, and if you look deeper, Amir Temur's diplomacy is a whole diplomatic theory. The Timurids also relied on the diplomatic legacy of Amir Timur and continued his work.

Amir Temur and the directions of Timurid foreign policy in science have not been thoroughly studied. After all, the full disclosure of this topic requires a separate and serious study. This topic is briefly and generally disclosed, sometimes partially in separate studies.⁵

⁴ Askarov A. Amir Temur and Khorezm. Abstracts of the international conference "Amir Temur and his place in world history". Tashkent, "Uzbekistan", 1996, pp. 39-40.

⁵ Umnyakov I.I. International relations of Central Asia at the beginning of the 15th century. Relations of Timur with Byzantium and France. Proceedings of UzGU. New series. issue 61. Historical faculty. Samarkand, 1956, 179-200

On the one hand, the fact that the threat from the Chingido-Mongols, who ensured the security of the borders, owning the Chigatai ulus, and seized the reins of government on the Great Silk Road, which personified politics, was still strong, necessitated the determination of delicate foreign directions.

Amir Temur's attack on Mongol tyranny created new problems for him. The situation required Amir Temur to determine foreign policy directions that were different from the powerful states of his time, such as Khorezm, the Golden Horde, Mongolia, Iran, Khorasan.

Amir Temur, along with the approval of Khorezm, which was part of the Chigatai ulus, including it in his state, wanted to strengthen the northern borders of his state, create a strong defensive space here. Because he wanted to protect his country from the great danger of the Golden Horde.

In our opinion, the direction of Amir Temur's foreign policy towards the Golden Horde embodied the following goals:

- firstly, to eliminate the threat from the Golden Horde in the north;
- secondly, to gain control over the northern branch of the Great Silk Road, one of the symbols of big politics;
- thirdly, to prevent the transformation of the Golden Horde into a powerful state and its transformation into a second-rate country;
- fourthly, to prevent the dominance of Iran and Azerbaijan;
- from the fifth to the northern part of Dashti Kipchak;
- sixth, strive to keep Khorezm under its control.

We observe that the relationship of Sahibgiron Amir Temur with the Golden Horde is one of the important political moments, and he seeks to improve and protect the state in all aspects and pursue the policy of the international big stick. Therefore, he put geostrategy at the forefront of diplomacy. The Ottoman state considered Egypt one of the main problems of its foreign policy.

The leaders of countries striving for a leading position in the world - the Sultan of Egypt Barquq, the Ottoman Sultan Bayezid Eldirim - tried to destroy him, and in addition tried to destroy Amir Temur along with the Golden Horde. Disputes over interests and territories had a great influence on tensions between them.

It is clear that although Amir Temur defeated Bayezid Eldirim, he gave his descendants one more chance - to remain on the throne.

Despite almost twenty years of conflict, there are no major battles between Egypt and the state of Amir Temur. He was not condescending to his enemies, he respected them under any circumstances.

Studies have shown that Amir Temur pursued a fair foreign policy:

- firstly, Amir Temur did not attack civilians for no reason and tried to resolve the issue as peacefully as possible;
- secondly, he guaranteed the peaceful coexistence of states based on the interests and rights of the people, the goals of establishing peace and cooperation are at the heart of his diplomatic thinking;
- Thirdly, he established relations of peace and cooperation with Western countries whose blood, race, religion and ideology are opposed to the East, and laid the cornerstone of the idea of Eurasia and integration.
- fourthly, if Jaloirs, Karakyunly, Bayazid and other relations with him, if not broken, then all the wide he did not rob so much;
- fifthly, the common sense of his servants gave away the opportunity and his enemies abused this opportunity;

- Sixth, he diplomacy science theoretical foundations strengthened, it is a new strategic tactics and exercise with closely related;
- seventh, he always gave priority to the rule of international equality;
- from the eighth set against yourself big remove the blockage with diplomatic intelligence did
- ninth, his in diplomacy a good person traits embodied;
- from the tenth - his diplomacy is fair and it was real diplomacy;
- Ten firstly, although he destroyed his opponent from the inside, he did not completely destroy him. Because his goal was not to destroy the enemy, but to call him to order;
- Ten secondly, his diplomatic activity Sahibkiran spiritual shows his peace, his incomparable mind, his genius.

Diplomatic Correspondence of Amir Temur and the Timurids with European Countries in the Soviet Period I.I. Despite the study by Umnyakov, the incomparable role of Sahibgiron in these diplomatic relations was not shown.⁶

Results.

The independence of our country literally created great opportunities for the study of correspondence written during the time of Amir Temur and the Timurids. In particular, the history of diplomatic correspondence began to be objectively studied by researchers. Serious research was also published in scientific monographs, brochures, collections.⁷

On the occasion of the 660th anniversary of Amir Temur, studies on diplomatic correspondence were published in the press.

help us understand the development of international relations and the causes of conflicts, as well as who followed the norms of diplomacy in relations, and who acted contrary to them. They are official primary source documents in our objective study of history.

Letters serve as a valuable source for us about the development of international relations of that time, the causes of international conflicts, as well as the norms of international rules for the use of diplomacy in relations and the level of their observance.

Studies have shown that Amir Temur unconditionally obeyed the norms of diplomacy under any circumstances;

The information in the letters shows that Sahibkiran gave his enemies many opportunities and time;

They are Amir Timur's unique evidence of his personality, courage, forgiveness;

In the Soviet period, "Amir Only walked during the invasion of Timur" interpreted as shallow It is quite impossible to agree with the thoughts, wherever he went a serious basis and reason for the letter content of this to the idea is proof.

Amir Timur's correspondence Turkey, Egypt, Tokhtamysh like big strategic states against the powerful military "alliance" directed against him without fighting through the events that he fought, that in the international arena the subtle political games that he left show. Correspondence, that's all, shows that his rules are roughly broken and belligerent policies carried out by enemies with suddenly no, depending on the situation individually get the preferred known.

Letters testify that nine-tenths of his victories were won by diplomacy, and another one by the sword.

Despite the fact that the Sultan of Egypt Amir Temur repeatedly killed the ambassadors, Sahibgiron repeatedly addressed Barquq and Faraj through diplomatic channels.

⁶ Mannonov B.S. Diplomacy of Amir Temur. Oriental Studies, 1996, pp. 10-37.

⁷ Сахибкиран и египетские султаны.-// Народная вода, 20 февраля 1996 г.

Amir Temur knew perfectly well that relations between the sultans would decide the fate of the people, and therefore he understood that the sultan should try to negotiate under any circumstances.

In our opinion, these historical values based on justice and law are of great practical importance not only for our country, but also for the coordination of international relations, and we must promote this heritage at the international level.

The inscriptions show that Sahibkiran, unlike other Muslim rulers of his time, was friendly towards foreign kings and considered them promising partners. He was well aware that in relations with European countries there are frequent exchanges of ambassadors, and friendship is strengthened through them, and merchants, entrepreneurs, who make a great contribution to the development of both countries, create great opportunities, and these events cause the development of both sides. To this end, he went down in history as a world leader who extended the hand of friendship and cooperation from the Muslim East to the West and removed the invisible wall between the East and the Maghreb. The letters indicate that the Host sought to strengthen and guarantee the rights of merchants and encouraged the kings to this worthy cause. The writings also show that he was a supporter of peace, peace and cooperation in international relations, and he himself was the initiator of this great work. He repeatedly called on European kings and eastern rulers for economic cooperation, sought to resolve this issue at the highest level and formalize these relations through agreements.

Summary.

Sahibkiran raised the science of diplomacy to the level of art, and this, of course, had a positive effect on international relations. The choice of the most suitable paths in the diplomacy of that time shows that the state wisdom of the Timurids rose to the level of art. Sahibkiran well understood that Islam is a pure idea that calls people to cooperation, peace and development, and not to militant actions, and used purely Islamic ideas in international relations.

It should be noted that the political and ethical aspects of Amir Temur's state administration are carefully developed and he embodies the theory of statehood. Such a political doctrine was important for strengthening the foundations of statehood during this period.

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